

ACOUSTIC CHARACTERIZATION OF ANTIBUBBLES FOR QUANTITATIVE IMAGING

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Traditional ultrasound contrast agent consists of gas microbubbles with a stabilizing shell. Theoretical analysis has shown that adding a sufficiently large liquid core to a gas bubble introduces asymmetry to its oscillations and, therefore, strongly increases nonlinear behavior [1]. Such bubbles with a liquid core are referred to as antibubbles. A recent paper compared the harmonic response of antibubbles to that of identical bubbles when insonified at a frequency of 1 MHz [2]. Our work extends upon this, adding multiple insonification frequencies in the range of 0.5-3 MHz with a step of 0.5 MHz, and comparing our results with those obtained with a traditional contrast agent, SonoVue (Bracco), approved for clinical use. Besides this, we present dynamic measurements of the scattered signal at the frequency identified to be the closest to antibubble resonance, producing time intensity curves (TICs) typically observed in vivo.

The configuration of our experimental setup, comprising a gelatin cuvette with the contrast-agent dilutions, an insonifying transducer (GE Panametrics), and a receiving hydrophone (Onda HGL), is similar to that in [2] (Fig.1). The position of the insonifying circular transducer (centered at 2.2 MHz) was adjusted by a motion stage such that the gelatin cuvette was positioned in the focus for every frequency studied. The hydrophone was used to record the scattered bubble signal at an angle perpendicular to the acoustic beam and a distance of 3 cm from the cuvette. For the dynamic measurements, the cuvette was replaced by a gelatin compartment, similar to the middle section of the gelatin cuvette, positioned horizontally. The flow through this compartment was generated by a continuous pump.

Compared to traditional contrast agents, stronger non-linear response at lower frequencies and high-quality TICs motivate further investigation of antibubbles for diagnostic applications.

Figure 1: side view of the setup.

Keywords

Antibubbles, harmonic response, time intensity curve

References

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